

TOMATO PESTS.

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Abstract: When growing tomatoes at home, we must take this into account. Tomatoes can be attacked by various types of pests. In this article, we will name some types of pests and tell you what treatments we can use to get rid of them.

Keywords: Aphid, Whitefly, Butterfly caterpillars, Red spider, Sair.

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We can encounter many pests in our garden. Usually, good treatment and some useful actions help to prevent them, but after infection, the culture shows different symptoms. We will deal with the most important ones, reminding you what are the symptoms and how to treat it to determine if our tomato is sick or infected with insects.

Tomato pests

We begin to name and analyze the various pests that can affect the tomato crop.

Aphid

Aphid is one of the most common diseases in tomatoes. You must be very careful not to damage our crops. And these insects feed on tomato juice and form fungi on the leaves. This type of fungus is called thick and covers a large part of the leaf surface, preventing them from carrying out photosynthesis well.

To prevent the appearance of aphids, you must first eliminate weeds that attract this type of insect. They are able to hide among them and attack our crops. We can also destroy them by maceration using nettle. To destroy the tongue, we need to spray the tomatoes or set some traps to catch them in flight.

White fly

This pest is the main cause of some diseases that attack our tomatoes. Like aphids, they feed on sap. The ideal conditions for their reproduction are high temperature and high humidity. It is common to see them in the summer and spring seasons where conditions are more favorable for them.

It is better to use chromatic traps to eliminate them and control populations. We can also use some hand-made infusions of absinthe and tansy. To repel these insects, we use crushed garlic and dilute it in water. Neem oil is a widely used product in agriculture and is very effective in killing pesky pests.

A very useful option is to plant some plants that help keep whiteflies away from our crops. These are shield plants and the best types for this are basil, Chinese carnation and calendula.

Butterfly caterpillars

Butterfly caterpillars are very harmful to our crops. They feed directly on the tomato and grow inside it. We can find tomatoes with large holes that are rotten and inedible.

Ecological and biological insecticides should be used to destroy these caterpillars. There are bacteria that serve to eliminate these problems and are not harmful to humans. Its use is completely natural, so we do not need pesticides or other chemical products.

Red spider

A spider mite is a type of mite that feeds on the sap of plants. To find out if our tomatoes are infected with this pest, we need to look at the underside of the leaves. They are usually divided into groups and are easy to recognize. If we find a leaf with a spider mite, it is better to tear it off and prevent it from infecting the rest of the plant. They usually appear due to an excess in the use of fertilizer. We can also use sulfur by spraying it on the plant.

Take a walk

The easiest way to determine the presence of thrips in our tomatoes is to see the appearance of green or yellow rings. It is better to place some traps in the form of posters or bottles painted blue to avoid the spread of the disease.

To always choose ecological solutions, it is better to use some animals that feed on these insects to destroy them naturally. Some of these animals are the wasp *Limes Noacki*, *Eretmocerus eremicus*, *Eretmocerus mundus* and the species *Encarsia Formosa*.

Conclusion: Harm: The most dangerous pest of tomatoes mainly feeds on the leaves, fruits, growth points, and root nodules of tomatoes and causes damage. Damaged fruits rot during the growing season.

Control measures: In field conditions, it is recommended to eliminate weeds belonging to the family of sycamores, destroy the affected plant parts, use biological methods of predatory weeds, entomopathogenic bacterial preparations and special insecticides.

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